

Antimicrobial Activity of *Bauhinia tomentosa* Linn. Plant Root Extracts Against Some Species of Bacteria and Fungus.

Soubhagya Lenka^{1*}, Sunit Kumar Sahoo², Debananda Champatisingh¹, Rakesh Kumar Pani³, Priti Murmu³, Manoranjan Sahu⁴

¹Dadhichi College of Pharmacy, Vidya-Vihar, Sudargram, Cuttack, Odisha.

²University Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Utkal University, Vani-Vihar, Bhubaneswar, Odisha.

³KIIT School of Pharmacy, KIIT University, Bhubaneswar, Odisha.

⁴Indira Gandhi Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Nayapalli, Bhubaneswar, Odisha.

ABSTRACT

Antibiotics are used to inhibit microbial growth and the progression of microorganisms within host cells, thereby preventing disease. In the present study, different extracts of the roots of *Bauhinia tomentosa* Linn. (Fabaceae) have been evaluated against Gram-positive (*Staphylococcus aureus*), Gram-negative (*Escherichia coli*) bacterial strains, and fungal (*Aspergillus niger*) strains using the zone of inhibition method. The hexane extract of the root showed the maximum antibacterial activity at a dose of 25 µg/ml, as compared with the standard drug (Ampicillin). The ethyl acetate extract at a dose of 25 µg/ml showed antifungal activity, as compared with the standard drug (Nystatin). The activities of these extracts of the roots of *B. tomentosa* are attributed to active phytochemical constituents, which showed antimicrobial potential, confirming the presence of flavonoids, tannins, steroids, etc.

Keywords *Bauhinia tomentosa*, antibacterial, antifungal, zone of inhibition.

INTRODUCTION

The presence of microbes long before the advent of mankind proves their viability. Microorganisms associated with diseases are more difficult to manage and treat with conventional medications. Conventional medications are associated with high cost, low potency, side effects, and long treatment duration. Therefore, the search for new, more effective antimicrobial agents is necessary to avoid complications [1,2]. Nowadays, herbal medicines are very popular for use in any kind of disease in both developing and developed countries. One of the most important species of this genus is *Bauhinia tomentosa* Linn. (Fam, Fabaceae). Certain *Bauhinia* species have a long history of traditional medicinal applications [3]. *Bauhinia tomentosa* is a scrambling, many-stemmed shrub or small tree, with branches that often drop and many slender twigs [4]. It has been reported to contain amino acids [5], proteins [5], fatty acids [6],

minerals [7], lectins [8], protocatechuic acid [9], phytohemagglutinins [10], rutin [11], quercetin [11], and isoquercetin [12].

However, no work has been done so far on the antimicrobial activity of the root of the plant. Hence, the present study was undertaken to investigate the antimicrobial activity of methanol, ethyl acetate, and hexane root extracts of *Bauhinia tomentosa* against two pathogenic bacterial strains, *Staphylococcus aureus* (G+ve) and *Escherichia coli* (G-ve), and a fungus, *Aspergillus niger*, using the zone of inhibition method. The corresponding solvents were used as solvent controls. The standard antibiotics, ampicillin 0.1 µg/disc and nystatin 0.1 µg/disc, were used as standards for bacteria and fungi, respectively.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant materials

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

The root of *B. tomentosa* was collected in November 2025 from the rural pockets of Chandaka Forest, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India, and identified by Prof. K. B. Satpathy, Department of Botany, CUTM, Centurion University, Odisha, India. The specimens of *B. tomentosa* (voucher number: 3182) were conserved in the herbarium for further use.

Extraction of Plant Materials

Freshly collected plant material (root) was washed with running tap water, shade-dried, and coarsely powdered. It was then extracted with n-Hexane, Ethyl acetate, and Methanol in a Soxhlet apparatus for 72 hours at a controlled temperature (50-60 °C). The extract was concentrated to dryness under reduced pressure until free of solvents. The yields of n-Hexane, Ethyl acetate, and Methanol were 2 gm, 17 gm, and 80 gm, respectively.

Preliminary phytochemical study:

The different root extracts were subjected to qualitative phytochemical analysis to detect the primary and secondary active metabolites in the plant for the recent investigational work.

Microbial Strains

Gram-negative bacteria, Gram-positive bacteria, and fungi from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC) were used in this study. Gram-negative bacteria, *Escherichia coli* (ATCC 25922); Gram-positive bacteria, *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC 25923); and the fungus, *Aspergillus niger* (ATCC 21232), were obtained from the National Chemical Laboratory, Pune, India.

Sterilisation

Sterilisation of media, water, etc., was carried out by autoclaving at 15 lbs/inch² for 20 minutes. The glassware, such as syringes, petri dishes, pipettes, and empty test tubes, was sterilised by dry heat in an oven at a temperature of 160 °C for 1 hour. The sterilised medium was cooled to 40 °C and poured into the petri dishes to contain 6 mm. The media was allowed to solidify at room temperature.

Preparation of Culture Medium for Bacteria:

Muller-Hinton agar media for bacteria	
Agar	2-2.5%
Meat extract	0.3%
Peptone	0.5%
Sodium chloride	0.5%
Distilled water	100ml
pH adjusted to	7-7.2

The above ingredients are dissolved in distilled water and heated for uniform mixing of agar, then the pH is adjusted to 7-7.2 and sterilised by autoclaving at 15lbs for 20 minutes.

Preparation of Culture Medium for Fungus:

Potato dextrose agar media for fungus	
Potato	20 gm
Dextrose	2.50 gm
Yeast extract	0.01 gm
Agar	2 gm
Distilled water	100 ml

The above constituents were dissolved in distilled water, and the pH was adjusted to 5.6±0.2 and then sterilised by autoclaving at 15 lbs for 20 minutes.

Antimicrobial Assay

Muller Hinton Agar and Potato Dextrose Agar (Hi-media) were prepared according to the manufacturer's instructions for the culture of bacteria and fungi, respectively. The two-test medium was sterilised by autoclaving at 121 °C for 15 minutes at 15 psi pressure. Sterile molten cool (45 °C) agar was poured aseptically into sterile Petri dishes (20 ml each), and the plates were allowed to solidify at room temperature in sterile conditions. After solidification and drying, the plates were seeded with appropriate microorganisms (bacteria and fungi) by streaking evenly onto the surface of the medium with a sterile cotton swab or pouring the appropriate microorganisms on the surface of a dry agar plate present in peptone broth. Care was taken for the even distribution of culture all over the plate. The inoculums were allowed to dry for 5 minutes. The discs of 5 mm diameter were prepared from Whatman filter paper No. 1 and were sterilised. The discs were then impregnated with the test extracts, control DMSO, ampicillin (0.1 µg/disc) for bacteria and nystatin (0.1 µg/disc) for fungus were used as

standards. Sterile Whatman No. 1 filter paper with different test concentrations ranging from 10-25 µg/ml was placed onto the agar with flamed forceps and gently pressed down to ensure contact, along with the diluted extract, and one appropriate control dry disc was also placed at the centre. Then the plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 hrs to allow perfusion of the drugs being tested. The next day, the zones of inhibition were measured with a measuring scale. The results were read by the presence or absence of a zone of inhibition. The inhibition ratios were calculated with the following formula.

$$\text{Inhibition ratio (\%)} = \frac{C - E}{C} \times 100$$

Where C = the average diameter of the largest and smallest colonies of the control groups.

E = the average diameter of the largest and smallest colonies of the experimental groups.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Identification of phytoconstituents of different root extracts of *B. tomentosa* was carried out by using different screening methods, and the inference showed the presence of different primary and secondary metabolites: steroid, saponin, triterpenoid, glycoside, carbohydrate, alkaloid, flavonoid, tannin, and protein [13]. The findings of phytochemical constituents are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of Phytochemicals in different root extracts of *B. tomentosa* Linn.

Sl. No	Name of Test	Hexane extract	Ethyl acetate extract	Methanolic extract
1	Test for Steroids	+	+	+
2	Test for Saponins	-	-	-
3	Test for Triterpenoids	+	+	+
4	Test for Glycosides	-	+	+
5	Test for Carbohydrates	-	+	+
6	Test for Alkaloids	-	-	-
7	Test for Flavonoids	-	+	+
8	Test for Tannins	-	+	+
9	Test for Proteins	-	+	+

(+) Present, (-) Absent

Antimicrobial activity study of different extracts of *B. tomentosa*

The results obtained in the present study revealed that various extracts of the plant part (root) possess potential antimicrobial activity against the two tested bacterial organisms (*E. coli*, *S. aureus*) and one tested fungus (*A. niger*). The methanolic root extract showed a broad spectrum of activity against all the bacterial

strains at the tested concentration of 20 µg/ml and 25 µg/ml in comparison with the standard drug ampicillin 0.1µg/disc and showed the remarkable antifungal activity at the tested concentration of against 10 µg/ml, 15 µg/ml, 20 µg/ml and 25 µg/ml in comparison with the standard drug nystatin 0.1µg/disc (Table 2 & Figure 1).

Antimicrobial Activity

Table 2: Antimicrobial Activity of Methanolic Root Extract of *B. tomentosa*

Test Organisms	M1 (in cm)	M2 (in cm)	M3 (in cm)	M4 (in cm)	S (in cm)
S.A.	1.4	2.7	2.8	3	2.1
E.C.	1.6	1.6	1.7	1.7	1.7
A.N.	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.5	0.9

M1-10µg/ml, M2-15µg/ml, M3-20µg/ml, M4-25µg/ml, S-Standard (Ampicillin 0.1µg/disc for S.A & E.C, Nystatin 0.1µg/disc for A.N)

Figure 1: Antimicrobial Activity of Methanolic Root Extract of *B. tomentosa*

Further study revealed that the ethyl acetate root extract showed remarkable antimicrobial activity. The tested concentration of 25 µg/ml unveiled higher antibacterial activity and antifungal activity than the standard drugs (Table 3 & Figure 2).

Table 3: Antimicrobial Activity of Ethyl Acetate Root Extract of *B. tomentosa*

Test organism	EA1 (in cm)	EA2 (in cm)	EA3 (in cm)	EA4 (in cm)	S (in cm)
S.A.	1.6	2.4	2.7	2.9	1.6
E.C.	1.6	2.0	2.0	2.1	1.7
A.N.	1.3	1.6	1.6	1.8	0.9

EA1-10µg/ml, EA2-15µg/ml, EA3-20µg/ml, EA4-25µg/ml, S-Standard (Ampicillin 0.1µg/disc for S.A & E.C, Nystatin 0.1µg/disc for A.N)

Figure 2: Antimicrobial Activity of Ethyl Acetate Root Extract of *B. tomentosa*

Furthermore, the hexane root extract showed the highest potency against the microbial organism growth at the tested concentration of 25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ with

respect to standard drugs and all the other extracts (Table 4 & Figure 3).

Table 4: Antimicrobial Activity of Hexane Root Extract of *B. tomentosa*

Test organism	H1 (in cm)	H2 (in cm)	H3 (in cm)	H4 (in cm)	S (in cm)
S.A.	1.9	2.6	3.0	3.2	1.6
E.C.	2.0	2.1	2.2	2.4	1.7
A.N.	1.2	1.4	1.4	1.5	0.9

H1-10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, H2-15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, H3-20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, H4-25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, S-Standard (Ampicillin 0.1 $\mu\text{g/disc}$ for S.A & E.C, Nystatin 0.1 $\mu\text{g/disc}$ for A.N)

Figure 3: Antimicrobial Activity of Hexane Root Extract of *B. tomentosa*

The antimicrobial activity has been screened because of their great medicinal relevance in recent years, infections have increased to a great extent, and resistance against antibiotics has become an ever-increasing therapeutic problem [14,15]. The presence of antifungal and antibacterial properties in plants is well established, as they have provided a source of inspiration for novel drug compounds, and plant-derived medicines have made a significant contribution towards human health. Plant-based antimicrobials have enormous therapeutic potential as they can serve the purpose without any side effects

that are often associated with synthetic antimicrobials. Continued research and exploration of plant-derived antimicrobials is needed today [16,17]. Many of the studies were useful in identifying the active principle responsible for such potentials and in developing clinically important therapeutic drugs for mankind. Hence, an attempt has been made to identify the antimicrobial activity of the root extract of *B. tomentosa*. Many plants have limitless ability to synthesise secondary metabolites, of which at least 12000 have been isolated. These substances serve as a plant defence mechanism against predation by

microorganisms, insects, and herbivores [18]. Many plants and their extracts are used against microbial infections due to the presence of secondary metabolites such as phenols [19], essential oils [20,21], terpenoids [22,23], alkaloids [24] and flavonoids [25]. In the present scenario, the emergence of multiple drug resistance in human pathogenic fungi and the small number of antifungal classes available stimulated research directed towards the discovery of novel antifungal agents from other sources, such as medicinal plants [26]. Aromatic and medicinal plants are known to produce certain bioactive molecules that react with other organisms in the environment, inhibiting bacterial or fungal growth (antimicrobial activity) [27,28].

CONCLUSION:

The plant extract studied could be an answer to people seeking better therapeutic agents from natural sources, which are believed to be more efficient with little or no side effects when compared to the commonly used synthetic chemotherapeutic agents. The present study verified the traditional use of *B. tomentosa* for various human ailments, especially for various infectious diseases. The presence of bioactive compounds such as flavonoids, tannins, triterpenoids in the ethyl-acetate and methanolic root extracts may be the reason for the antimicrobial activity. The literature revealed the flavonoids formed a complex with bacterial cell wall and the tannins may cause some enzyme inhibition properties in microorganisms by interacting with sulfhydryl groups with some specific and non-specific proteins. Thus, this plant could be utilised as an alternative source of useful antimicrobial drugs. Further studies are needed to isolate, characterise, and elucidate the structure of the bioactive compounds of this plant for antimicrobial drug formulation.

REFERENCES

1. Anonymous: The Wealth of India, Raw Material. 1988;11:55.
2. Penna C, Marino S, Vivot E, Cruanes M.C, Munoz J.D, Cruanes J, Ferraro G, Gutkind G and Martino V. Antimicrobial activity of Argentina plants used in the treatment of infectious diseases. Isolation of activity compounds from *Sebastiania brasiliensis*. J. Ethnopharmacol. 2001;77:37-40.
3. Valdir CF. Chemical Composition and Biological Potential of plants from the genus *Bauhinia*. Phytother Res. 2009;23:347-54.
4. Orwa C, Mutua A, Kindt R, Jamandass R, Anthony S. Agroforestry Database: A tree reference and selection guide, version 4.0. 2009. Available from: <http://www.worldagroforestry.org/sites/treedbs/treedatabases>. [cited 2010 Jan 31].
5. Agbede JO. Chemical analysis of leaf meal and processed seed flours of an aesthetic plant: *Bauhinia tomentosa*. J Food Agric Environment. 2007;5:233-5.
6. Daulatabad CD, Mulla GM, Mirajkar AM. Vernolic acid from *Lagerstroemia thomsonii* and *Bauhinia tomentosa* seed oils. J Oil Technol assoc India. 1991;23:53-4.
7. Chowdhury AR, Banerji R, Misra G, Nigam SK. Fatty acid composition and mineral composition of the seeds of some species of *Bauhinia*. Feete Seifen Anstrichmittel. 1984;86:237-9.
8. Rao CK, Satyanand N, Rama G. Pollen lectins. J plant sci res. 1991;6:1-5.
9. Nageshwar G, Anuradha SM, Radha Krishnaiah M, Narayana LL. Distribution pattern of phenolic constituents in species of *Bauhinia* Linn. and its taxonomic significance. Proceedings Indian academy of Sciences - Plant Sci. 1986;96:1-7.
10. Khanna AL. Lectins: Biology, Biochemistry and Chemical Biochemistry. 1982;2:701-9.
11. Row LR, Viswanadham N. Coloring matter of the flower petals of *Bauhinia tomentosa*. Proceedings. Indian Academy of Sciences, Section A. 1954;39:240-2.
12. Subramanina SS, Nair AG. Isolation of isoquercitrin from flowers of *Bauhinia tomentosa*. Indian J. Chem. 1963;1:450.
13. Sofowora A. Screening Plants for Bioactive Agents. In: Medicinal Plants and Traditional Medical in Africa. 2nd Edition, Spectrum Books Ltd., Sunshine House, 1993; 2: 134-156.
14. Austin, D.J., Kristinsson, K.G. and Anderson, R.M., The relationship between the volume of antimicrobial consumption in human communities and the frequency of resistance. Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA. 1999;96:1152-6.
15. Venkatesan D and Karrunakaran CM. Antimicrobial activity of selected Indian

- medicinal plants. *Journal of Phytology*. 2010;2(2):44–48.
16. Toona L, Kambu K, Ngimbi N, Cimanga K and Vlietinck AJ. Antiamoebic and phytochemical screening of some Congolese medicinal plants. *J. Ethanopharmacol.* 1998;61:63-71.
17. Srivastava J, Lambert J and Vietmeyer N. Medicinal plants: An expanding role in development. *World Bank Technical Paper*. 1996; 320.
18. Wink M. Plant breeding: importance of plant secondary metabolites for protection against pathogens and herbivores. *Theoretical and Applied Genetics*. 1998;75:225-233.
19. Kazmi MH, Malik SA, Hameed N, Ali AS and Ali NS. Plant products as antimicrobial agents. *Phytochemistry*. 1994;36:761-763.
20. Cosentino S, Tuberoso CIG, Pisano B, Satta M, Mascia V, Arzedi E and Palmas F. In vitro antimicrobial activity and chemical composition of Sardinian thymus essential oils. *Letters in Applied Microbiology*. 1999;29:130-135.
21. Daferera DJ, Ziogas BN and Polissiou MG. The effectiveness of plant essential oils in the growth of *Botrytis cinerea*, *Fusarium sp.* and *Clavibacter michiganensis* subsp. *michiganensis*. *Crop Protection*. 2003;22:39-44.
22. Habtemariam S, Gray AI and Waterman PG. A new antibacterial sesquiterpene from *Premna oligotricha*. *Journal of Natural Product*. 1993;56:140-143.
23. Taylor RSL, Manandhar NP, Hudson JB and Towers GHN. Screening of selected medicinal plants of Nepal for antimicrobial activities. *J. Ethanopharmacol.* 1995;61:57-65.
24. Omulokoli E, Khan B and Chhabra SC. Antiplasmodial activity of four Kenyan medicinal plants. *Journal of Ethanopharmacology*. 1997;56:133-137.
25. Batista O, Duarte A, Nascimento J and Simões MF. Structure and antimicrobial activity of diterpenes from the roots of *Plectranthus hereroensis*. *Journal of Natural Product*. 1994;57:858-861.
26. Elisabetsky E and Souza GC. Etnofarmacologia como ferramenta na busca de substâncias ativas. In: C.M.O. Simões, *Farmacognosia da planta ao medicamento*, UFRG e UFSC, Porto Alegre/Florianópolis. 2004:107-122.
27. Chopra RN, Nayer SL and Chopra IC. *Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants*, 3rd Edn. New Delhi: Council of Scientific and Industrial Research. 1992:7-246.
28. Bruneton J. *Pharmacognosy, Phytochemistry, Medicinal plants*. France: Lavoisier Publishing Co. 1995:265-380.

HOW TO CITE: Soubhagya Lenka, Sunit Kumar Sahoo, Debananda Champatisingh, Rakesh Kumar Pani, Priti Murmu, Manoranjan Sahu, Antimicrobial Activity of *Bauhinia tomentosa* Linn. Plant Root Extracts Against Some Species of Bacteria and Fungus., *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, 2 (4), 1751-1757. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19641455>

